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Abstract

The LCOE report presents the final modelled levelized cost of electricity for the MegaRoller technology applied through oscillating wave surge converter devices. The technology and the related innovations developed during the project are reviewed in the report, and the methodology used in calculating the LCOE is presented. Discussion and limitations of the results are given and prospects for further costs reductions are examined.

Table of Contents

	Page
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1 INTRODUCTION	9
2 INNOVATION BEHIND THE LCOE REDUCTION	10
2.1 PTO hardware.....	10
2.2 PTO control system	11
3 METHODOLOGY.....	13
4 RESULTS	15
4.1 Levelized cost of electricity	15
4.2 Unit cost breakdown	15
4.3 Sensitivity analysis.....	16
5 DISCUSSION.....	18

Table of Figures

	Page
Figure 1 MegaRoller unit.	9
Figure 2 PTO modular structure.	10
Figure 3 PTO hydraulic accumulator rack arrangement.	10
Figure 4 Prediction algorithm mimicking the auditory cortex of the brain.	11
Figure 5 Project contributions to decrease LCOE.	12
Figure 6 MegaRoller LCOE.	15
Figure 7 Division of MegaRoller WEC unit costs.	16
Figure 8 MegaRoller LCOE sensitivity to discount rate (base rate of 7,4 %).	17
Figure 9 Learning rates of power production technologies from 2010 to 2019.	19

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The novel MegaRoller technology represents state-of-the-art solution for unlocking the potential in wave energy. The European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme funded MegaRoller project has been an effort to develop the power take-off component for a 1 MW oscillating wave surge wave energy converter and consequently decrease the levelized costs of electricity for the technology type. The project has spearheaded development of wave energy conversion technologies and sought to facilitate the uptake of wave energy as an alternative technology in the production of renewable energy.

Several innovations in the design of hardware and software components of the PTO have been achieved resulting in a notable decrease in the levelized costs of electricity for the technology type.

The achieved range of levelized costs of energy for the MegaRoller technology is 148-100 EUR/MWh. Further costs reductions are expected to be realized through increased deployments of the technology and to follow a costs reduction trajectory similar to other variable renewable energy technologies. Following 50 MW of cumulative deployment LCOE is forecast to reach 116-60 EUR/MWh and in the most conservative assessment decline below 100 EUR/MWh after 130 MW deployed capacity. Assuming an average 20 % learning rate throughout development, the cost of the MegaRoller technology will reach parity with the current lowest cost solar PV and onshore wind projects at 23 EUR/MWh.

The ability of the MegaRoller technology to supplement other renewable energy technologies in the electricity mix and to extract a higher value per produced kilowatt hour has also been modelled. As wave power is not correlated with the day-night-cycle of solar radiation nor the local wind climate determining wind power production, wave energy can support a power grid with increased solar and wind production capacity and proportionately deployed claim a higher price per kWh produced.

The development of the PTO technology for OWSC technologies carried out through the MegaRoller project and the achieved results are highly encouraging for further decrease of costs and uptake of wave energy.

1 INTRODUCTION

The MegaRoller project is a European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme funded consortium effort to decrease the levelized costs of electricity (LCOE) of oscillating wave surge converter technologies (OWSC) through enhancements in hardware and control algorithms of the power take-off (PTO) system. Aim of the project is to design, build and validate a high performance, cost efficient and reliable PTO for a 1 MW capacity WEC based on WaveRoller technology.

The project objectives have been structured into four areas and monitored by key performance indicators. The MegaRoller project aims to reduce the LCOE of the system below 150€/MWh, by increasing nominal device capacity, reducing and standardizing the number of components, increasing the PTO reliability and reducing power conversion losses.

This report reviews the MegaRoller technology and the achieved innovations impacting the LCOE of the system and presents the achieved levelized cost of electricity for the technology.

Technology description

The MegaRoller WEC unit is based on WaveRoller technology commercialized by AW-Energy. The technology uses a bottom-hinged oscillating panel which follows the surge movement of the water particles in the nearshore area, in water depth of 10–25 m. The device is anchored to the seabed and depending on tidal conditions it is mostly or fully submerged. Wave energy converted into motion by the panel is transmitted through a drivetrain to the PTO.

Figure 1 MegaRoller unit.

The MegaRoller PTO converts the wave induced oscillations from mechanical energy to electricity. It consists of two-cylinder units and one standardized power unit. As the panel moves back-and-forth, the PTO's hydraulic pistons pump hydraulic fluids inside a closed hydraulic circuit inside a hermetic structure. These cylinders are composed of single action pistons, one cylinder acting when the panel moves towards the coast, and another when the movement has the opposite direction. These high-pressure fluids are fed into a hydraulic motor that drives an electricity generator. The cylinders are sealed in a watertight compartment and are not exposed to the marine environment. The cylinders use the mechanical power applied to the pistons to compress the hydraulic fluid and store it in the accumulators. The accumulators help to attenuate the variation of the power produced, caused by the irregular profile of the incident waves. The energy stored in the accumulators is transferred through pressurized hydraulic flow to a hydraulic motor, followed by an electric generator that converts it into electrical energy. The electrical output is then connected to substation at shore and the electric grid via a subsea cable.

2 INNOVATION BEHIND THE LCOE REDUCTION

During the MegaRoller project several new innovations in the design of OSWC PTO design have been achieved that have resulted in decreased costs for the technology. These are divided in PTO hardware and PTO control systems innovations and listed and described below.

2.1 PTO hardware

Modular PTO design: The design of the MegaRoller is modular in two ways. There is a modular structure in the arrangement the main units: two PTOs on both sides of the panel and the Central Power Unit. Also, the internal component arrangement of the PTO is highly modular. The greatest advantage of modularity inside the PTO is that the modules can be exchanged and adjusted for MegaRoller WEC according to varying wave resource, ambient conditions (e.g. sea water temperature) and customer requirements. Modularity is an advantage also regarding assembly and maintenance.

Figure 2 PTO modular structure.

Novel accumulator arrangements: The MegaRoller PTO has hydraulic accumulators within the PTO units. The accumulators are connected to the system in racks. An accumulator rack is assembled using a rack assembly manifold, which is a thick machined carbon steel plate that has multiple accumulator connections and one large connection to the system. The manifold can be easily modified for different size racks and to have connections for accumulators on either one or two sides.

Figure 3 PTO hydraulic accumulator rack arrangement.

All accumulators in the PTO are mechanically identical and they have different prefill pressure levels depending on the location and purpose of the accumulator. Modular accumulator arrangement enables power smoothing and provides a possibility to contribute to grid frequency regulation as a part of wave energy farm.

Intelligent cylinder: Three concepts were designed to remove pressure spikes from the MegaRoller hydraulic cylinder circuit. These concepts utilize mechanical shock absorbers, additional force control valves and elastic lines.

Standardized central power unit: The purpose of the electric central unit is to connect the two PTO units of the MegaRoller WEC and feed the power to the grid. All communication routes between the PTO units and between the substation and the PTOs are also routed via the central unit. The Central Unit will have a cylinder-shaped hull with detachable round end flanges in both ends. In most cases, a round cylindrical shape in underwater structure provides the best weight-cost-volume ratio since it is easy to manufacture and naturally has good endurance against external pressure variations.

Twin drive trains: The MegaRoller twin drive train consists of two drive trains: one on each side of the panel, inside the PTO housing. As the PTO moment is applied from both sides of the panel there must be some resilience to compensate for panel bending, thermal expansion and panel bearing wear. As a result of the conceptual mechanical design (Conceptual Mechanical Design, D2.5) resilient mounting concepts enabling the usage of twin drive trains have been developed. To summarize, the drive train arrangement makes it possible to utilize two PTOs with a single panel and increase the rated power to 1MW.

2.2 PTO control system

Wave-by-wave prediction: A machine-learning algorithm to produce wave-by-wave predictions is integrated in the MegaRoller PTO control systems software to give an input to damping algorithm. The algorithm predictions are used in PTO damping control for optimized power capture. This algorithm is based on Echo State Networks (ESN), a relatively new scheme for training highly nonlinear recurrent neural networks to perform time series prediction. The ESN has been modified by adapting methods from computational neuroscience building the ESN to mimic the auditory cortex of the brain. New ways of training the ESN were also developed.

Figure 4 Prediction algorithm mimicking the auditory cortex of the brain.

Wave-by-wave damping control: By applying wave-by-wave damping it is possible to capture significantly more energy from the moving panel. The input for the damping algorithm is the wave estimate given by the wave prediction algorithm.

Advanced energy storage control: An efficient energy storage control based on modelling the fill level of the hydraulic accumulators has been developed. Based on the information of the incoming waves (the wave prediction) and the fill level of accumulators, usage of the energy storage can be optimized. Depending on the predicted size of waves coming in, the output power of the device can be adjusted be able to, on the other hand store all the energy coming, but also to keep the output power adequately stable.

Advanced efficiency control: Advanced efficiency control is a combination of controlling multiple PTO subsystems in optimized way. The subsystems include cylinder packs, accumulators, motor-generator packs, and cooling.

Supervisor controller: The supervisor controller controls site output power and grid support functionality, e.g. frequency regulation. The controller is a PLC connected via fast data transfer channel to individual devices, enabling real-time control. The parametrization of the supervisor controller is done in SCADA, and the controller operates autonomously based on those parameters.

The adjustable parameters in the supervisor controller are:

- Responsiveness to weather change
- Grid monitoring triggers
 - o Shutdown
 - o Grid support (frequency regulation, with required and available power levels)
- Amount of reactive power to be produced

Figure 5 Project contributions to decrease LCOE.

3 METHODOLOGY

LCOE is a measure of the average net present cost of electricity generation for a generating plant over its lifetime. The LCOE is calculated as the ratio between all the discounted costs over the lifetime of an electricity generating plant by a discounted sum of the actual energy delivered. The result equals a price of electricity required for the revenue of project to equal its costs.

The formula used for calculating the LCOE of renewable energy technologies is:

$$LCOE = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N \frac{I_t + M_t + F_t}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^N \frac{E_t}{(1+r)^t}}$$

- I = Investment expenditures
- M = Maintenance and operations expenditures
- F_t = Fuel expenditures
- E_t = Electricity generation
- R = Discount rate
- N = The expected lifetime of the system
- t = Time variable

Life-cycle costing of the MegaRoller device has been carried out as a part of the project and a specialized tool developed to assess the costs of the technology. The life-cycle costing is based on a detailed cost breakdown structure that divides the total life cycle cost into relevant categories and further into concrete cost parameters that are much easier to estimate than the total cost. The highest level of the hierarchy is a life-cycle phase and the lowest level is formed by the parameters for which numerical values are given. Regarding the maintenance of the MegaRoller device, there are two main types of maintenance tasks which are necessary to keep the technology functioning: scheduled maintenance and corrective or unscheduled maintenance. Scheduled maintenances are divided into minor and major periodic maintenances as well as inspections. The process and the specialized tool developed are presented in detail in a separate project report *D5.6 LCC assessment report of the MegaRoller device*. The life-cycle costing tool has been utilized in assessing the cost and LCOE for MegaRoller technology.

Building renewable energy capacity is a capital-intensive engagement. However, as these facilities, including wave energy farms, use a free energy resource in the production of electricity, the fuel expenses for these plants are zero. In relation to technologies relying on fuel combustion, the capital costs for renewable energy projects are therefore proportionately larger. Because of this the cost of capital (i.e. “the expected rate of return that market participants require in order to attract funds to a particular investment”¹) or discount rate have a considerable impact on the final cost of energy.

The cost of capital for renewable energy projects depends on various factors such as the country of implementation, regulatory risks, uncertainties related to the variability of the harnessed energy resource and the robustness of the deployed technology. In this report, an average discount rate for onshore wind energy projects within OECD countries is assumed and a sensitivity analysis on its variation presented in chapter 4.3.

¹ S.P. Pratt and R.J. Grabowski (2014) *Cost of Capital: Applications and Examples*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

In the LCOE assessment costs related to project and site development have been excluded as these are highly dependent on the country and region of implementation, availability of baseline data and are poorly related to the scale of the development. These costs include elements such as licensing and other authority fees.

Electricity generation from the MegaRoller device is calculated by factoring the wave energy resource at the site of deployment, the power efficiency of the system and its operational hours. Key parameters for defining electricity production of the MegaRoller device are presented in article *Life Cycle Assessment of an Oscillating Wave Surge Energy Converter*² published in relation to the MegaRoller project.

A general guideline of assessing the potential learning curve³ is applied whereby the learning rate for the MegaRoller technology is expected to be between 20% and 10%. The higher learning rate corresponds to a manufacturing process in which machining accounts for roughly a fifth with the remainder being carried out as a hand assembly. An example of such an industry is shipbuilding where several similarities can be drawn to the manufacturing process of a MegaRoller-technology -based WEC. Although 20 % can be considered a steep learning rate it is well within the parameters of renewable energy technologies as presented in Figure 9. A slower learning rate of 10 % is corresponding to offshore wind.

² Apolonia, M.; Simas, T. Life Cycle Assessment of an Oscillating Wave Surge Energy Converter. J. Mar. Sci. Eng. 2021, 9, 206

³ Stewart, R., Wyskida, R. & Johannes, J. (1995) Cost Estimator's Reference Manual, 2nd Edition, John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Levelized cost of electricity

The LCOE analysis presented herein has been carried out within the parameters of the MegaRoller project considering a 10-unit, 10 MW deployment. The achieved range of levelized costs of energy for the MegaRoller technology is 148-100 EUR/MWh, which is aligned with the set targets for the project.

The MegaRoller LCOE is expected to decrease with increased deployments of the technology through further costs reduction and improvements in energy capture and conversion. Learning curves from other mature industries provide base assumptions for estimating future LCOE of the MegaRoller technology, the progression of which is presented in Figure 6. Two learning curves are applied of 10 % and 20 % representing the range of possible in the MegaRoller LCOE development with increased capacity.

Figure 6 MegaRoller LCOE.

Following 50 MW of cumulative deployment LCOE is forecast to reach 116-60 EUR/MWh and in the most conservative assessment decline below 100 EUR/MWh after 130 MW deployed capacity. Assuming an average 20 % learning rate throughout development, the cost of the MegaRoller technology will reach parity with the current lowest cost solar PV and onshore wind projects at 23 EUR/MWh.

4.2 Unit cost breakdown

The division of costs for a single MegaRoller WEC unit is presented in Figure 7. Costs of the MegaRoller system itself including the assembly and deployment, account for 80 % of the costs, with the PTO being the single most impactful cost driver in the technology.

Figure 7 Division of MegaRoller WEC unit costs.

For the 20-year, single unit project the operational expenditure was estimated to account for 20 % of the total costs. Major maintenance herein signifies scheduled maintenance during which the unit is re-floated to the surface and momentarily not in operation. Other operation and maintenance elements include costs such as insurance, land lease, maintenance facilities, security services and waste management.

4.3 Sensitivity analysis

Cost of capital

Provided the limited deployed capacity of wave energy projects to date there are uncertainties in relation to the cost of capital for the first commercial projects to be executed and consequent discount rate to be used in the calculations. The average cost of capital of new solar PV, onshore and offshore wind deployed through the years 2000 to 2017 has been documented to be in the range of 4.8 % to 8.3 %.⁴ Including projects deployed in non-OECD countries the rates can hike up to a cap of 10.2 %.

Base discount rate used in the MegaRoller LCOE analysis is 7,4 %. For the 10-unit MegaRoller array deployment the sensitivity analysis of the cost of capital is presented in Figure 8. For a larger wave energy project, the cost range will be significantly larger as investment expenditure increases.

⁴ Steffen, B. (2020) Estimating the cost of capital for renewable energy projects, Energy Economics, 88/ 104783

Figure 8 MegaRoller LCOE sensitivity to discount rate (base rate of 7,4 %).

Even for a smaller-scale array it is notable that the change one percentage point in the discount rate impacts the LCOE by roughly 3,5 %. This stands to highlight the importance of reducing the perceived technology risks for further costs reduction.

5 DISCUSSION

Project scope focused on a single technology component

The MegaRoller project has focused on the design, demonstration and validation of the PTO for the OWSC technologies. Designs for the MegaRoller device panel, the foundation solution and the surrounding plant infrastructure have been conceptualized during the MegaRoller project however these have not been designed in any significant detail. As the MegaRoller system constitutes the single most significant cost factor for the LCOE there are notable costs reductions possibilities in optimizing the system beyond the PTO which will in part drive further the costs reductions of the technology. For this analysis estimates of the remaining technology components costs have been conservatively assessed based on the First-Of-A-Kind WaveRoller deployment in Portugal 2019.

The value of wave energy

One of the main challenges in LCOE as a metric to evaluate the real costs of renewable energy is its inability to account for the intermittency in electricity production. Due to the variability of renewable energy production, backup generation and/or storage are often needed to balance the grid. These accrue additional cost which are accounted in the LCOE. Additionally, in markets with dynamic pricing models, LCOE can obscure competition based on time of day.

As the penetration of wind and solar capacities in grids are increasing, production that occurs in other times than during the peak daylight hours or during high winds – when supply is low – has a higher value. Wave power is not correlated with the day-night-cycle of solar radiation nor the local wind climate determining wind power production, and the resource is enhanced during the winter months when solar production is diminished. Consequently, wave energy can support power grid with increased solar and wind production capacity and proportionately deployed claim a higher price per kWh produced.

A study simulating the inclusion of wave energy in a Western Mediterranean power system and market concluded that electricity production with wave energy has a positive correlation to power market prices, whereas wind and solar power have a negative correlation. On average wave power would net 6 % and 2 % better price for production than wind and solar power respectively⁵

Considering smaller-scale use-cases for the technology and isolated power grids the challenges with the intermittency of renewable energy are generally more pronounced therefore the value of wave energy in such systems could be even higher. Furthermore, the deployment of solar and wind power across coastal economies is only expected to increase thereby increasing the value of wave energy.

Learning curve

Notwithstanding the challenges of LCOE to assess the true costs of renewable power generation, the development of next generation PTO technology for OWSC technologies carried out through the MegaRoller project and the achieved results are highly encouraging for further decrease of costs and uptake of wave energy.

Through continuing technology development, initial deployments and scale-up of projects, the MegaRoller technology is expected to follow costs reduction trajectory aligned with other renewable

⁵ Vrana, T. "Levelized Value of Energy for Wave Power", Case study presentation, Ocean Energy Europe 2019, Dublin Ireland, 1.10.2019

energy technologies. The decrease of utility-scale solar photovoltaics is the most prominent example of these possibilities with an 82 % decrease in costs over the last 10 years⁶. In fact, since the deployments of solar PV reached 1 MW capacity in the 70s the price of solar modules has declined by over 99 %⁷. The learning rate of solar PV has been a staggering 36 %, i.e. as deployed capacity for the technology has doubled, costs have decreased by 36 %.

Wind power alike has followed the decreasing cost trend with increasing deployments of capacity with a learning rate of 23 %. Figure 9 shows the LCOE development of electricity production technologies over cumulative deployments during the past decade.

Figure 9 Learning rates of power production technologies from 2010 to 2019⁸.

According to IRENA, in 2019 there were 531 MW of installed marine energy capacity⁹ the majority of which coming from a few tidal ranges with wave energy deployments surmounting to a mere few megawatts. As such wave energy technologies are yet to truly enter the process of learning-by-doing. Costs reductions through increased deployments, experience and time are well document across industries and here wave energy is no different.

⁶ IRENA (2020), Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2019, International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi.

⁷ Our World in Data (2020) < <https://ourworldindata.org/cheap-renewables-growth>>

⁸ Our World in Data (2020) < <https://ourworldindata.org/cheap-renewables-growth>>

⁹ IRENA (2020), Renewable capacity statistics 2020, Abu Dhabi

It is unreasonable to expect the MegaRoller technology to follow a cost reduction curve as steep realized for Solar PV, however historical data from similar technological innovations provide reasonable basis for these assumptions. The forecast learning curves and their impact on MegaRoller LCOE are presented above in Figure 6.

Low life-cycle emissions

To undercut emissions from power generation renewable energy production must foremost have low emissions throughout their lifetime. Life-cycle assessment of the MegaRoller device has been carried out as a part of the project to ensure least carbon intensive design and benchmark the device with other power generation technologies. The carbon intensity of MegaRoller is 33.8 g CO₂ eq/kWh and energy intensity 432 kJ/kWh which are aligned with other variable renewable energy production sources and very low in comparison to production relying on fuel combustion¹⁰.

¹⁰ Apolonia, M.; Simas, T. (2021) *Life Cycle Assessment of an Oscillating Wave Surge Energy Converter*. J. Mar. Sci. Eng., 9, 206